

New universal type of interface in the magnetic insulator/topological insulator heterostructures

Sergey V. Eremeev,^{*,†,‡,¶,§} Mikhail M. Otrokov,^{||,⊥,‡,¶} and Evgueni V. Chulkov^{§,||,‡,¶}

[†]*Institute of Strength Physics and Materials Science, Tomsk, 634055, Russia*

[‡]*Tomsk State University, Tomsk, 634050, Russia*

[¶]*Saint Petersburg State University, Saint Petersburg, 198504, Russia*

[§]*Donostia International Physics Center (DIPC), Paseo de Manuel Lardizabal, 4, 20018 San Sebastián/Donostia, Basque Country, Spain*

^{||}*Departamento de Física de Materiales UPV/EHU, Centro de Física de Materiales CFM - MPC and Centro Mixto CSIC-UPV/EHU, 20080 San Sebastián/Donostia, Spain*

[⊥]*IKERBASQUE, Basque Foundation for Science, 48011 Bilbao, Spain*

E-mail: eremeev@ispms.tsc.ru

Abstract

Magnetic proximity effect at the interface between magnetic and topological insulators (MIs and TIs) is considered to have great potential in spintronics as, in principle, it allows realizing the quantum anomalous Hall and topological magneto-electric effects (QAHE and TME). Although an out-of-plane magnetization induced in a TI by the proximity effect was successfully probed in experiments, first-principles calculations reveal that a strong electrostatic potential mismatch at abrupt MI/TI interfaces creates harmful trivial states rendering both the QAHE and TME unfeasible in practice. Here on the base of recent progress in formation of planar self-assembled single layer MI/TI heterostructure (T. Hirahara, et al., *Nano Lett.* 2017, 17, 3493-3500), we propose a conceptually new type of the MI/TI interfaces by means of density functional theory calculations. By considering MnSe/Bi₂Se₃, MnTe/Bi₂Te₃, and EuS/Bi₂Se₃ we demonstrate that instead of a sharp MI/TI interface clearly separating the two subsystems it is energetically far more favorable to form a built-in interface via insertion of the MI film inside the TI's surface quintuple layer (e.g., Se-Bi-Se-[MnSe]-Bi-Se) where it forms a bulk-like MI structure. This results in a smooth MI-to-TI connection that yields the interface electronic structure essentially free of trivial states. Our findings open a new direction in studies of the MI/TI interfaces and restore their potential for the QAHE and TME observation.

Keywords

Topological insulators; Magnetic insulators; vdW-type interface; Magnetic proximity effect; Topological heterostructures; DFT calculations

Understanding the interfacial physics and underlying atomic scale structure is fundamentally important for many technological problems such as catalysis, epitaxial growth of the thin films, adhesion, surface phase transformations and many others. Among them the formation of interfaces between novel kind of materials, topological insulators (TIs) and magnetic solids is one of the very actual challenges. Since the discovery of three dimensional topological insulators, the time-reversal symmetry breaking and surface band gap opening have been considered as core ingredients for the observation of novel phenomena like image magnetic monopole¹ or quantum anomalous Hall effect (QAHE),²⁻⁸ as well as for the realization of TI-based devices. Of the two approaches extensively used to break the time-reversal symmetry in TIs or at their surfaces, i.e. the doping by transition metal atoms⁹⁻¹⁵ and the magnetic proximity effect via formation of the interface with magnetic insulator,¹⁶⁻²² the latter has such advantages against the former as spatially uniform magnetization and absence of the dopant-induced scattering.²³ The out-of-plane exchange field, induced in a TI due to an MI proximity, has been experimentally probed in a number of structures containing low Curie temperature insulating ferromagnets such as $\text{Cr}_2\text{Ge}_2\text{Te}_6/\text{Bi}_2\text{Te}_3$,²⁴ $\text{EuS}/\text{Bi}_2\text{Se}_3$ ^{16,25-27} and $\text{EuS}/\text{Sb}_{2-x}\text{V}_x\text{Te}_3$.²¹ These studies have revealed that in the particular case of $\text{EuS}/\text{Bi}_2\text{Se}_3$ the magnetism can survive up to room temperature,²⁵ despite the fact that the Curie temperature of the bulk EuS is only 17 K. Furthermore, in contrast to the in-plane magnetic anisotropy of the bulk EuS, an out-of-plane magnetization has been observed for $\text{EuS}/\text{Bi}_2\text{Se}_3$.^{16,25} Both of these observations have been explained by the proximity effect of the topological surface state of Bi_2Se_3 that enhances the perpendicular magnetic anisotropy and increases the strength of the exchange coupling in the Eu layer.²⁸ Unfortunately the electronic structure of these buried interfaces remains experimentally uncharacterized since they are inaccessible to a standard angle-resolved photoemission spectroscopy. In this situation the density functional theory (DFT) calculations is an important available tool for an accurate electronic structure description. It has been found that for both the $\text{EuS}/\text{Bi}_2\text{Se}_3$ ^{28,29} and $\text{MnSe}/\text{Bi}_2\text{Se}_3$ ^{20,30} heterostructures, the electrostatic potential difference

between MI and TI causes the charge redistribution and hybridization at the interface, leading to drastic modifications of the TI's electronic structure: instead of the expected single, gapped Dirac state, its coexistence with trivial interface states has been revealed in the bulk gap region. These states are confined within the interfacial quintuple layer (QL) of Bi_2Se_3 and slowly decay into MI. At the same time, the topological state relocates from the interface region to distant atomic layers of the TI film escaping much the layers with induced magnetization.

Recently it has been demonstrated that the massive Dirac state can be achieved in the $\text{MnBi}_2\text{Se}_4/\text{Bi}_2\text{Se}_3$ planar heterostructure prepared by co-depositing Mn and Se on top of the molecular beam epitaxy (MBE) grown film of Bi_2Se_3 .³¹ It has been found that the well-ordered hexagonal MnBi_2Se_4 septuple layer (SL) is formed spontaneously on the base of a nominal MnSe bilayer and the Bi_2Se_3 's topmost QL due to diffusion of deposited atoms into the latter. The MnBi_2Se_4 layer thus formed is free from inhomogeneity as is clearly determined by low energy electron diffraction (LEED) measurements. Accordingly, the DFT calculations confirm that it is energetically more favorable to incorporate the MnSe bilayer into the Bi_2Se_3 QL and form a MnBi_2Se_4 SL rather than to keep the bilayer on top of the QL. The gapped Dirac state in this planar heterostructure is localized predominantly within the SL and thus the Mn layer interacts strongly with the topological surface state due to the spatial overlap of the respective wave functions that provides a large magnetic gap of ~ 100 meV. In fact, the penetration of the topological state into the MnBi_2Se_4 SL block allowed the observation of a clear Dirac point gap opening at the MI/TI interface using angle-resolved photoemission spectroscopy (ARPES). The out-of-plane magnetization in the $\text{MnBi}_2\text{Se}_4/\text{Bi}_2\text{Se}_3$ planar heterostructure revealed by the superconducting quantum interference device (SQUID) and X-ray magnetic circular dichroism (XMCD) measurements³¹ is consistent with an intralayer ferromagnetic (FM) ordering predicted by DFT calculations for the rhombohedral bulk MnBi_2Se_4 .³²

The $\text{MnBi}_2\text{Se}_4/\text{Bi}_2\text{Se}_3$ heterostructures have also been obtained with a slightly different MBE technique.³³ It has been demonstrated that the introduction of an elemental beam of Mn during the MBE growth of Bi_2Se_3 results in the formation of randomly distributed MnBi_2Se_4 SLs in the Bi_2Se_3 matrix instead of the expected dilute magnetic compound $\text{Bi}_{2-x}\text{Mn}_x\text{Se}_3$. Unfortunately, the incorporation of the MnBi_2Se_4 SLs inside the Bi_2Se_3 film in an ordered fashion is hardly possible with this method. In contrast, the approach based on the prefabricated Bi_2Se_3 film and Mn-Se co-deposition³¹ in principle allows synthesizing the $[(\text{MnBi}_2\text{Se}_4)_{(m\text{SLs})}/(\text{Bi}_2\text{Se}_3)_{(n\text{QLs})}]_p$ superlattices with well-defined n , m , and p what can be done using a layer-by-layer growth of Bi_2Se_3 QLs with the subsequent Mn and Se co-deposition. The latter technique also allows potential realization of the recently proposed planar MI/TI heterostructures on the base of SLs of the related compound, MnBi_2Te_4 .³⁴ Incidentally, it has been predicted and experimentally confirmed to be the first antiferromagnetic TI very recently.³⁵ Soon after, the synthesis of the MnBi_2Te_4 thin films have been reported precisely using the approach of Ref. 31: each SL of the MnBi_2Te_4 film has been formed based on the prefabricated Bi_2Te_3 QL and further Mn-Te co-deposition.³⁶ In fact, both the MnBi_2Se_4 and MnBi_2Te_4 compounds, predicted to have the same crystal and magnetic phases,³² are structurally and compositionally compatible with a number of the tetradymite-like TIs and therefore are of great potential for construction of the SL-based MI/TI heterostructures that can be considered as a magnetic extension of the TI surface.^{34,37} In such systems, the interface between an MI SL and the underlying TI QL is provided by the van der Waals coupling similar to that in the tetradymite-like TIs what guarantees the absence of a strong interface potential and allows penetration of the Dirac state into the MI SL resulting in a giant gap due to a strong exchange interaction with magnetic moments of the Mn atoms occupying a complete atomic layer in the SL block. This is in stark contrast with the above described cases of the $\text{MnSe}/\text{Bi}_2\text{Se}_3$ and $\text{EuS}/\text{Bi}_2\text{Se}_3$ heterostructures in which the formation of an abrupt interface not only produces trivial states, but also leads to a relocation of the Dirac state into the deeper lying QL.^{20,28,29}

The formation of one or another type of the interface may strongly depend on the growth conditions. In the EuS/Bi₂Se₃ heterostructure synthesis it has been opted for the MI growth at room temperature,^{16,25} which, according to Ref. 25, suppresses Eu and S diffusion. This procedure yields relatively thick EuS layers (up to 3-4 nm without deterioration) and an atomically sharp EuS/Bi₂Se₃ interface.^{16,25} In contrast, when Mn atoms have been deposited on Bi₂Se₃ at 240 °C in a Se-rich condition,³¹ a thin film of MnBi₂Se₄ has been formed, showing the van der Waals type of coupling to the TI substrate below it.

Here, using relativistic DFT calculations, we propose a fundamentally new type of the interface between an MI film and a tetradymite-like TI, that appears to be universal for binary magnetic insulators, as exemplified by MnSe/Bi₂Se₃, MnTe/Bi₂Te₃, and EuS/Bi₂Se₃. The fabrication of the proposed interface suggests a growth mechanism implying a sinking of the co-deposited MI atoms into the outermost QL of the TI substrate and formation of the MnSe(Te) or EuS structure combined with few remnant atomic layers constituted the outermost QL of a TI surface: Se(Te)-Bi-Se(Te)-[MnSe(Te)]-Bi-Se(Te) or Se-Bi-Se-[EuS]-Bi-Se. Such a scenario is by far more energetically favorable than that of the sharp interface formation and covalent type bonding to a TI.^{16,25,28,29} Strikingly, the realization of this scenario leads to a unique situation when the heterostructure's magnetic part, based on a material that intrinsically does not show van der Waals bonding (MnSe, MnTe, EuS, etc), turns out to be van der Waals coupled to a TI substrate since the MI film is actually sandwiched between Se(Te)-Bi-Se(Te)/-Bi-Se(Te) layers. As we show, this yields the interface electronic structure free of trivial states in the bulk band gap and, in the case of the out-of-plane magnetization, provides the Dirac point gap opening. We believe that the key to the realization of these unusual but energetically stable interfaces might be in finding the appropriate growth conditions, that should probably resemble those used in Ref. 31. Moreover, this scenario of the MI/TI growth can be easily verified in the experiment by the analysis of chemical composition of the outermost layers of the MI/Bi₂Se₃(Bi₂Te₃) heterostructures to identify the Bi atomic layer. These findings enable efficient engineering

Figure 1: Equilibrium atomic structures of the $\{(MnSe)_N\}/Bi_2Se_3$ heterostructures with magnetic blocks containing N from 1 to 8 MnSe bilayers.

of the MI/TI interfaces with tailor-made properties and pave a way to realization of the quantum anomalous Hall and topological magnetoelectric effects as well as their exotic consequences, such as image magnetic monopole or Majorana fermions, on the basis of the MI/TI heterostructures.

Results

We start with the MnSe/ Bi_2Se_3 interface. In Ref. 31, it was theoretically demonstrated that a freestanding $MnBi_2Se_4$ SL is by 630 meV per two-dimensional unit cell energetically more favorable as compared to the $[MnSe \text{ bilayer}]/Bi_2Se_3$ -QL system. In the experiment, this indeed results in formation of the $MnBi_2Se_4$ SL under the Mn-Se co-deposition on the Bi_2Se_3 surface.³¹ Leaving outside the scope of the present work the diffusion mechanism of penetration of the deposited atoms inside the QL (which in fact requires a separate thorough consideration), we further compare the energy of the $MnBi_2Se_4$ SL with a MnSe bilayer

(BL) placed on top of it with the nonuple layer (NL) block with a nominal composition $\text{Mn}_2\text{Bi}_2\text{Se}_5$ and find the latter to be by more than 600 meV favorable. Thereby, the further deposition of Mn and Se atoms onto the MnBi_2Se_4 surface should result in formation of the Se-Bi-Se-[MnSe]₂-Bi-Se block (hereinafter denoted as $\{(\text{MnSe})_2\}$). Among the magnetic configurations in the NL, the FM ordering is by about 5 meV/(Mn pair) less favorable than the interlayer antiferromagnetic (AFM) state. Further calculations show that for each additional MnSe BL its immersion in the previous block is energetically much more favorable than the ontop BL position. At the same time, the stability of the interlayer AFM ordering increases, the energy difference with respect to the FM state approaching the value of 27.25 meV/(Mn pair) for $N = 8$ (i.e. for 8 MnSe BLs). Thus the magnetic configuration of the MnSe film sandwiched between Se-Bi-Se-/-Bi-Se layers is the same as in the bulk MnSe, where Mn magnetic moments are ordered antiferromagnetically along the [111] direction of the NaCl-type lattice³⁸ which corresponds to z direction in our heterostructures. The equilibrium atomic structures for the heterostructures with magnetic blocks containing from 1 to 8 MnSe BLs built into the originally outermost QL of the Bi_2Se_3 surface are shown in Figure 1. Thus, the co-deposition of Mn and Se atoms on the Bi_2Se_3 surface may allow to obtain not only the planar heterostructure $\text{MnBi}_2\text{Se}_4/\text{Bi}_2\text{Se}_3$,³¹ but also a new type of the MI/TI system in which a relatively thick MnSe film is sandwiched between Se-Bi-Se-/-Bi-Se bilayers to form a $\{(\text{MnSe})_N\}$ block that is van der Waals coupled to a TI. In such heterostructures the interface between MnSe film and Bi_2Se_3 substrate is effectively formed inside the newly formed $\{(\text{MnSe})_N\}$ block unlike the previously assumed model with an abrupt interface²⁰ located in between the QL and the MnSe layer. The smooth interface inside the $\{(\text{MnSe})_N\}$ block should guarantee the absence of the strong interface potential whereby the trivial interface states should not arise (contrary to the $\text{MnSe}/\text{Bi}_2\text{Se}_3$ heterostructure case²⁰), while the vacuum side of the heterostructure that, similarly to the Bi_2Se_3 surface is terminated with a -Bi-Se BL, should not support the formation of dangling bonds.

Unlike the $\text{MnBi}_2\text{Se}_4/\text{Bi}_2\text{Se}_3$ heterostructure, in which the MnBi_2Se_4 (i.e. $\{(\text{MnSe})_1\}$)

Figure 2: The gapped Dirac state in the $\{(\text{MnSe})_N\}/\text{Bi}_2\text{Se}_3$ heterostructures with $N = 1$ (a), $N = 2$ (b), and $N = 3$ (c). The red and blue points correspond to the states with in-plane spin polarization perpendicular to the wavenumber (positive and negative, respectively) that are localized at the topmost SL and the neighboring QL. Dependence of the band gap width on N (d). (e–l) Spatial distribution of the gapped Dirac state for $N = 1, 8$. Shaded region corresponds to the Bi_2Se_3 part of the heterostructure. Vertical black lines mark positions of the Bi and Se atomic layers, while the green lines show the Mn layers.

block demonstrates FM ordering,³¹ the $\{(\text{MnSe})_N\}$ block with $N > 1$ can be a compensated (an uncompensated) interlayer antiferromagnet when the number of MnSe bilayers N is even (odd). Such an alternating magnetic structure of the $\{(\text{MnSe})_N\}$ block affects the gap in the topological interface state. Indeed, while the $N = 1$ $\text{MnBi}_2\text{Se}_4/\text{Bi}_2\text{Se}_3$ heterostructure has a Dirac point gap of 81 meV (Figure 2(a)), the one with $N = 2$, featuring the compensated AFM order in the $\{(\text{MnSe})_2\}$ block, demonstrates the gap of 10.4 meV only, see Figure 2 (b). However, once a nonzero magnetization in the $\{(\text{MnSe})_N\}$ block is recovered for $N = 3$, the gap increases to 39.7 meV (Figure 2 (c)). In general, as can be seen in Figure 2 (d),

the gap in the Dirac state demonstrates oscillatory behavior with increasing N converging towards the value of ~ 21 meV, where heterostructures with an odd/even number of MnSe bilayers in the block correspond to the maxima/minima in the oscillatory curve. Such an oscillating behavior is related to the spatial localization of the gapped Dirac state. In the $\text{MnBi}_2\text{Se}_4/\text{Bi}_2\text{Se}_3$ ferromagnetic heterostructure ($N = 1$), the Dirac state penetrates into the magnetic block (70% of the Dirac state is localized in the SL, see Figure 2 (e)) and hybridizes noticeably with the Mn orbitals that is the reason for a large gap in this system. It is worth noting that the Dirac state, being localized in the main part near the van der Waals gap between the SL and the upper Bi_2Se_3 QL, nevertheless has a significant weight in the outer Bi and Se layers of the SL. In the heterostructure with a compensated AFM $\{(\text{MnSe})_2\}$ block (Figure 2 (f)) the Dirac state also significantly penetrates into the NL although its weight on the vacuum side is reduced. In the middle part of the NL the Dirac state overlaps slightly differently with the Mn layers possessing oppositely oriented magnetic moments which explains a non-zero (though small) gap in the system with zero total magnetic moment. With increasing N in the $\{(\text{MnSe})_N\}$ block (Figures 2 (g-l)) one can see no changes in the massive Dirac state localization at the interface between the Bi_2Se_3 QL and $\{(\text{MnSe})_N\}$. Inside the N -BL block, the state spreads over the MnSe layers and the vacuum-side tail gradually disappears with the increase of N . Since the odd N blocks possess non-zero magnetic moment the overlap of the Dirac state with Mn layers produces relatively larger magnetic splitting. On the other hand, the overlap is larger for the Mn layers lying closer to the main charge density allocation (near the van der Waals spacing between the $\{(\text{MnSe})_N\}$ block and the QL beneath) whereas the distant Mn layers contribute significantly less to the exchange splitting which explains the fact that the gap tends to a constant value with increasing the MnSe film thickness in the $\{(\text{MnSe})_N\}$ block.

A related heterostructure $\text{MnBi}_2\text{Te}_4/\text{Bi}_2\text{Te}_3$ as constructed from SL film of magnetic insulator MnBi_2Te_4 ³⁹ on top of structurally and compositionally compatible topological insulator Bi_2Te_3 has recently been proposed.³⁴ It demonstrates an FM out-of-plane ordering

in Mn layer resulting in 77 meV gap in the Dirac spectrum.³⁴ As was pointed out above, this heterostructure can potentially be grown by the technique used for the $\text{MnBi}_2\text{Se}_4/\text{Bi}_2\text{Te}_3$ heterostructure fabrication,³¹ i.e. by co-deposition of Mn and Te atoms on top of Bi_2Te_3 film. Indeed, as our total energy calculations show, MnBi_2Te_4 SL is by 505 meV energetically more favorable than $[\text{MnTe-BL}]/\text{Bi}_2\text{Te}_3\text{-QL}$. Continuing Mn-Te “co-deposition” one can expect the formation of relatively thick film of MnTe sandwiched between Te-Bi-Te-/-Bi-Te bilayers like in the case of the $\{(\text{MnSe})_N\}/\text{Bi}_2\text{Se}_3$ heterostructure. However, despite the fact that MnTe is chemically similar to MnSe, it has a hexagonal lattice of the NiAs type⁴⁰ with A-B-A-C atomic layers stacking sequence which differs from A-B-C stacking in NaCl-structured MnSe(111) film. Considering additional MnTe BL on top of MnBi_2Te_4 SL (Figure 3 (a)) we find that it is by more than 500 meV energetically unfavorable as compared to the NL structures with MnTe BL built into the middle of the block irrespective of the type of the stacking (NiAs or NaCl) or the magnetic coupling between Mn layers. Among the NL structures, the one with the NiAs-like stacking of the atomic layers turns out to be more stable, gaining 93 meV relative to the NaCl-like structure. At that, the former structure favors the interlayer AFM groundstate, resembling that of the bulk MnTe with NiAs lattice, while the realization of the metastable NaCl-like structure would lead to the FM alignment between the two Mn layers. Next, when the number of MnTe bilayers N increases to 3, the $\{(\text{MnTe})_3\}$ block is forming and the NiAs stacking shown in Figure 3(d) again appears to be more favorable (by 99 meV) than that NaCl.

It is known that below the Néel temperature, which is 310 K⁴¹ in bulk and thick films of MnTe, the magnetic structure consists of ferromagnetically ordered Mn planes which are antiferromagnetically stacked along the c -direction, the easy axis being locked in the basal plane.^{42–45} Our estimations show that in-plane easy axis is also preferred in the $\{(\text{MnTe})_N\}$ block starting from $N=2$. Since the out-of-plane spin component is necessary for the formation of the Zeeman splitting in the Dirac state, the $\{(\text{MnTe})_N\}/\text{Bi}_2\text{Te}_3$ heterostructures with $N > 1$ do not meet this requirement. However, as was shown experimentally,²⁵

Figure 3: Atomic structures of the (a) MnTe BL on top of the MnBi₂Te₄ SL, (b,c) {(MnTe)₂} NL block with the NaCl- (b) and NiAs- (c) type stacking in the MnTe part, and (d) {(MnTe)₃} block with the NiAs-type stacking.

for the EuS/Bi₂Se₃ heterostructure, which we will consider below, the MI film magnetic anisotropy is changed within near interface region (≈ 1.5 nm) from the bulk-like in-plane to out-of-plane direction. This modification was explained as a consequence of the strong coupling with topological Dirac state.^{25,28} In principle we can not exclude such effect for the {(MnTe)_N}/Bi₂Te₃ heterostructures, however, it requires thorough experimental studies of the magnetism in this system.

Finally, we consider the EuS/Bi₂Se₃ heterostructure, which appears to be the most studied MI/TI system both from experimental and theoretical sides.^{16,25,28,29} In spite of the magnetic proximity effect reported for the EuS/Bi₂Se₃ heterostructures, neither the quantum anomalous Hall nor topological magnetoelectric effects have been observed in this system. Unfortunately, the experimental electronic structure of the interface is unknown. However, the theoretical calculations, performed using the model of the abrupt interface,^{28,29} show the formation of the trivial spin-polarized states that completely close the bulk projected band gap, what, possibly, hinders the observation of the above-mentioned effects. To explore the possibility of formation of the smooth EuS/Bi₂Se₃ interface that does not create the harmful

Figure 4: (a) Relaxed atomic structures built on the base of the EuS bilayer and Bi₂Se₃ QL. (b) Atomic structures for the EuS BL on top of the {(EuS)₁} (left) and for the {(EuS)₂} blocks (right).

trivial states, we start again with a minimum structure consisting of the freestanding Bi₂Se₃ QL with a EuS bilayer adsorbed on top of it (Figure 4 (a)). Considering two possible EuS BL orientations (first and second structures in Figure 4 (a)), we find that the structure in which Se and S layers are facing each other is by 673 meV less favorable than the structure with Eu-Se bonding. We note that adding several QLs to the bottom and several EuS BLs to the top of the latter structure will result in formation of the abrupt interface EuS/Bi₂Se₃ heterostructures considered earlier.^{28,29} However, the interchange of Bi and Eu atoms, as indicated by red arrow in the second structure, will lead to formation of the third structure with lowering the total energy by 974 meV. Such a large energy gain for sinking of the Eu layer into the Bi₂Se₃ QL should undoubtedly indicate the advantage of the structural transformation. Next step, i.e. the interchange of Se and S atoms, as indicated by red arrow in the third structure, further lowers the total energy by 275 meV and results in formation of the septuple layer structure (the fourth structure in Figure 4 (a)) with EuS bilayer incorporated in the middle part of the former QL of Bi₂Se₃. Considering the energy difference between the latter structure and the one with the EuS BL on top one can realize that it reaches 1.25 eV, which is twice as large as compared to the corresponding energy

Figure 5: Band structures (a,d), the slab atomic configurations (b,e), and the squared modulus of the wave-functions ($|\Psi|^2$) for the Dirac state at the top (pink) and the bottom surface (gray) of the slab (c,f) for the $\{(\text{EuS})_N\}/\text{Bi}_2\text{Se}_3$ heterostructures with $N = 1$ (a-c) and $N = 5$ (d-f). In panels (a) and (d) the spin polarization is shown for the interface Dirac state in red and blue circles (positive and negative, respectively). The states localized at the bottom surface of the slab are indicated in gray. The shaded area shows the bulk band structure projection of Bi_2Se_3 substrate. The inset shows a close-up of the dispersion near the Dirac point. In panels (c) and (f) blue lines show Eu layers while black lines mark positions of the other atomic layers.

difference in the MnSe-based system. Since the MnBi_2Se_4 SL was experimentally realized one can suppose that deposition of the Eu and S atoms on $\text{Bi}_2\text{Se}_3(0001)$ will result in formation of the $\{(\text{EuS})_1\}$ SL. Further, like in the case with the $\{(\text{MnSe})_N\}$ blocks, we have continued the “deposition” of magnetic bilayers. For the situation shown in Figure 4 (b), the total energy difference between the structure with a EuS BL on top of the $\{(\text{EuS})_1\}$ SL and the structure with a double BL in the middle part of the $\{(\text{EuS})_2\}$ block amounts to 1.57 eV, being even larger than for the first BL sinking and thus making the formation of the EuS film sandwiched by remnant layers of the initial Bi_2Se_3 QL very profitable as compared to the abrupt $\text{EuS}/\text{Bi}_2\text{Se}_3$ interface.

To elucidate the formation of the massive Dirac state in the $\{(\text{EuS})_N\}/\text{Bi}_2\text{Se}_3$ heterostructures and its dependence on the magnetic film thickness we have constructed slabs containing Bi_2Se_3 film of 5 QLs thickness with $\{(\text{EuS})_N\}$ blocks on top for $N = 1, \dots, 5$. It is worth

noting that in our electronic band structure calculations we have assumed the out-of-plane magnetization similar to the one observed in the experiment.²⁵ The calculated band structure for the $N = 1$ heterostructure is shown in Figure 5 (a). The spectrum demonstrates the existence of two Dirac states near the Fermi level: the massless Dirac cone of the pristine bottom surface (gray points and gray line in inset) and the massive Dirac state with a gap $D_g=3.8$ meV at the top surface. Unlike the EuS/Bi₂Se₃ heterostructures with an abrupt interface^{28,29} there are no other states in the Bi₂Se₃ band gap and thus the spectrum is qualitatively similar to that in MnBi₂Se₄/Bi₂Se₃ heterostructure.³¹ The quantitative difference with respect to the latter system is that the gap in the interface Dirac state in [EuS]₁-Bi₂Se₃/Bi₂Se₃ is much smaller. This is due to the facts that the interface Dirac state penetrates into the {(EuS)₁} block to a lesser extent than in the MnBi₂Se₄/Bi₂Se₃ case (50 vs. 70 %) and that the strongly localized Eu-*f* orbitals hybridize weakly with the topological state. Despite the smaller gap, the {(EuS)_N}/Bi₂Se₃ spectrum is characterized by a non-trivial Chern number, similarly to the case of the Mn-based SL heterostructure.

In contrast to the {(MnSe)_N}/Bi₂Se₃ case, in the heterostructure with the {(EuS)_N} ferromagnetic block we did not find significant dependence of the gap in the interface Dirac state on the increasing N . The D_g is almost the same in the heterostructures with $N = 2$ and $N = 3$ (3.8 meV vs. 3.9 meV, respectively), while it becomes slightly smaller (3.5 meV) with $N = 3$, and takes a value of 3.2 meV for $N = 4$ and $N = 5$ (Figure 5 (d)). It is evident that further increase of a number of the EuS bilayers in the {(EuS)_N} block does not change the gap width since the interface state does not reach even the third Eu layer (Figure 5 (f)). Comparing these results to those reported for the abrupt EuS/Bi₂Se₃ interface in Ref. 29, one notes that, first, in the latter case the Dirac point gap is negligibly small (if any) and, second, this gap coexists in energy with the trivial spin-polarized interface states what makes the overall spectrum gapless. This is in stark contrast to the smooth {(EuS)_N}/Bi₂Se₃ interface featuring finite D_g values and showing no trivial states within the projected bulk band gap region (Figure 5 (a,d)).

Conclusions and outlook

Using the density functional theory calculations we have proposed a novel type of the interface between a magnetic insulator (MI) and a topological insulator (TI) of the Bi_2Se_3 family. The strategy of the interface preparation implies the immersion of the epitaxially-deposited MI atoms into the surface quintuple layer of a TI resulting in formation of the MI film sandwiched by the remnant layers of this quintuple layer. Our calculations show that, if the stacking of the atomic layers in the bulk phase of the MI differs from the stacking in the hosting quintuple layer, the encapsulated magnetic film tends to adopt its bulk-like atomic structure starting already from a thickness of a few bilayers. Moreover, the total energy calculations also reveal the bulk-like magnetic ordering trend even for the relatively thin films inserted inside the quintuple layer. By inserting more MI bilayers in the "grown-in" film, we have successively increased its thickness up to a couple of nanometers finding each insertion to be very much energetically favorable as compared to the case of a bilayer standing on the surface. Altogether, it proves such systems to constitute a novel type of the MI/TI interface, rather than the magnetic extension^{31,34} of a tetradymite-like TI by a thin film of the magnetic block-layered compound.³²

The new type of the interface proposed in the present work differs fundamentally from the previously realized²⁵ and theoretically studied^{20,28,29} abrupt MI/TI interface, that implies a simple joining of the two materials by their surfaces. Indeed, the immersion growth of a magnetic film results in formation of the *smooth* MI/TI interface with the bonding occurring inside the newly formed block and not at its surface. This guarantees the absence of a strong interface potential producing harmful trivial interface states characteristic of the MI/TI heterostructures with the abrupt interface. Therefore, a fully gapped electronic structure appears at the smooth MI/TI interface thus providing conditions for realization of the quantum anomalous Hall and topological magnetoelectric effects. Although in some cases the Dirac point gap might be larger for the smaller thicknesses of the encapsulated MI film, a compromise between the gap size and the magnetic critical temperature (which

is expected to tend to the bulk value with the increase of the film thickness), appears as an optimal strategy for realization of those effects at elevated temperatures.

The feasibility of this new type of the MI/TI interfaces is supported by the recently demonstrated growth of the $\text{MnBi}_2\text{Se}_4/\text{Bi}_2\text{Se}_3$ heterostructure.^{31,33} Moreover, the remnant pnictogen and chalcogen layers of the TI quintuple layer over the growing-in MI film can be easily verified in the experiment by analyzing the surface chemical composition of the forming heterostructures using Auger electron spectroscopy or X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy. Incidentally, the suggested mechanism of the epitaxial growth on the layered TI surfaces is apparently not restricted by the considered here $\text{MnSe}/\text{Bi}_2\text{Se}_3$, $\text{MnTe}/\text{Bi}_2\text{Te}_3$, and $\text{EuS}/\text{Bi}_2\text{Se}_3$ systems but is rather general for epitaxial growth on TI substrates. Indeed, recently the CoFeB films have been grown on the $\text{Bi}_2\text{Te}_3(0001)$ and $\text{Bi}_2\text{Se}_3(0001)$ substrates by laser molecular beam epitaxy and by using XPS measurements it has been found that at the surfaces of the grown 10-nm-thick metallic films the Bi and Te(Se) atoms are present.⁴⁶

Methods

For structural optimization and electronic band calculations we used the Vienna Ab Initio Simulation Package^{47,48} with generalized gradient approximation (GGA-PBE)⁴⁹ to the exchange-correlation potential. The interaction between the ion cores and valence electrons was described by the projector augmented-wave method.^{50,51} The Hamiltonian contains scalar relativistic corrections, and the spin-orbit interaction (SOI) is taken into account. The in-plane lattice constant of the heterostructure was fixed to that of Bi_2Se_3 . DFT-D3 van der Waals corrections⁵² were applied for accurate structure optimization. To correctly describe the highly correlated Mn- d and Eu- $4f$ electrons we include the correlation effects within the GGA+ U method as developed in Ref.⁵³ For Mn- d electrons we include the correlation effects within the GGA+ U method in the Dudarev implementation⁵⁴ where we have chosen the $U^* = U - J = 5.33(5.34)$ eV values to be the same as in bulk MnSe(MnTe).⁵⁵ For Eu- $4f$

electrons the values of U and J parameters were taken from results of the constrained random phase approximation (cRPA) calculations⁵⁶ where U and J was found to be of 9.1 and 0.7 eV, respectively. The Chern number calculations were based on tracking the evolution of Wannier charge centers (WCCs) for all occupied bands as realized in Z2Pack.⁵⁷

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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